

Quantum Averaging and Two Velocities

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In quantum mechanics, one may describe a free particle moving forward or backward by $\exp(ikx)$ where k is positive or negative. Mathematically, momentum is given by applying $-i\hbar d/dx$ and kinetic energy by $-\hbar^2/2m d^2/dx^2$ to $\exp(ikx)$ and then by dividing by $\exp(ikx)$. On the other hand, if there is a potential, one has a wavefunction $W(x) = \sum_p f_p \exp(ipx)$ which is based on 'interference'. Furthermore, this interference affects averages i.e. the application of $-i\hbar d/dx W/W$ and $-\hbar^2/2m d^2/dx^2 W/W$. In particular, the 'average' momentum $-i\hbar d/dx W/W$ is not zero for a particle in a box as it would be for a classical object bouncing back and forth elastically. In addition, average momentum squared divided by $2m$ is not equivalent to the kinetic energy average i.e. $-\hbar^2/2m d^2/dx^2 W/W$. Furthermore, the change in space of $-i\hbar d/dx W/W$, the average momentum, would seem to be related to an acceleration, but rather is related to the quantum kinetic energy average and the change in density. It is the second derivative d^2/dx^2 Quantum Ave(p) which is related to force. In addition, the first order change in spatial density is related to the quantum average momentum, the second to the quantum average kinetic energy and the third to a term proportional to classical force and a term proportional to the product of quantum average kinetic energy and quantum average momentum. We attempt to examine these features in this note.

Interference

For a quantum wavefunction (bound state) $W(x) = \sum_p f_p \exp(ipx)$, with the particular potential determining f_p through the Schrodinger equation. It seems, however, that 'direct' interference occurs in the wavefunction i.e. at a point x , a p_1 may lead to $\cos(p_1x)$ being positive while $\cos(p_2x)$ is negative. This feature carries over into averages such as $-i\hbar d/dx W/W$ or $-\hbar^2/2m d^2/dx^2 W/W$ and so is physically important. For a single particle moving to the right or left, one may write $\exp(ikx)$ where k is positive or negative. Then, momentum is given by $-i\hbar d/dx \exp(ikx)/\exp(ikx) = \hbar k$ and kinetic energy by $-\hbar^2/2m d^2/dx^2 \exp(ikx)/\exp(ikx) = \hbar^2 k^2/2m$. For a particle in a box, all p states are excited by collisions with the wall, but the overall wavefunction is $\sin(kave x)$. The quantum average momentum is then $-i\hbar d/dx \sin(kave x)/\sin(kave x)$.

One may ask why the classical result would not apply i.e.:

$$-i\hbar d/dx \exp(ikx)/\exp(ikx) - i\hbar d/dx \exp(-ikx)/\exp(-ikx) = 0. \quad ((1))$$

If the particle is classical i.e. exists at point x at time t , then even if there exists a kind of periodic motion $\exp(ipx)$, one would expect ((1)) to hold. It seems the periodic motion $\exp(ipx)$ affects particle motion in space i.e. the particle is not a point, but exists within a wavelength at least i.e. $p = 2\pi/\text{wavelength}$. In other words, there is uncertainty related to space and time. Classically a particle moves with momentum k as it approaches a wall. After a collision lasting from t_1 to $t_1 + \delta$, it reflects elastically. Such does not seem to be the case in quantum mechanics. Part of the particle (in terms of probability), it seems, may be moving towards the wall, while part

is already reflecting. Thus, there may be an actual interference which would also affect the average momentum. In other words, one would write:

$$(i\hbar/dx \exp(ikx) - i\hbar/dx \exp(-ikx)) / (\exp(ikx) + \exp(-ikx)) \quad ((2))$$

This seems to define quantum averaging. One may also use such an average for kinetic energy, namely:

$$KE_{ave}(x) = (\text{Sum over } p \text{ of } p^2/2m \exp(ipx)) / (\text{Sum over } p \text{ of } \exp(ipx)) \quad ((3))$$

Interestingly, $KE_{ave}(x)$ satisfies a classical conservation of energy law which is equivalent to the bound state Schrodinger equation:

$$-1/2m \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} W + V W = E W \quad ((4))$$

A priori, one may ask at least two questions at this point. First, why should a classical conservation law hold for the quantum kinetic energy average and secondly, why is $\frac{1}{2} m (-i\hbar/dx W/W)^2$ not equivalent to this kinetic energy?

One may argue that ((4)) holds experimentally, but it seems there are also hints leading to this equation. Consider an even wavefunction, the potential ax^2 and a displacement from $x=0$ to $x=\delta$.

At $x=\delta$ $V(0+\delta) = a(\delta)^2$ i.e. the change in the potential is second order in δ . The first order change is 0. Thus, by conservation of energy, the first order change in kinetic energy should also be 0 or kinetic energy to first order at $0+\delta$ should equal to kinetic energy at $x=0$.

Consider the quantum average of kinetic energy:

$$-1/2m \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} W(\delta) / W(\delta) = KE(\delta)$$

If $d/dx W = 0$ at $x=0$, then $W(\delta) = W(0) + .5 \delta^2 (d/dx d/dx W)$ evaluated at $x=0$ ((5))

Taking $-1/2m \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx}$ of W/W where $\delta=x$:

$$KE(x=\delta) = KE(x=0). \quad ((6))$$

Thus, the quantum average kinetic energy seems to satisfy a conservation of energy equation with $V(x)$ for this example. This does not prove that it must always do so, but it is suggestive.

Properties of $-i\hbar/dx W / W$

As argued in other notes, in quantum bound states there seems to be an average momentum equal to $-i\hbar/dx W/W$. For a particle bouncing classically back and forth between two walls, there would be no such average momentum, it would be zero. Similarly, there would be no spatial density as a function of x . In quantum mechanics, the average momentum $i\hbar/dx W/W$ seems to be related to spatial density changes i.e.

$$d/dx \text{ spatial density} = d/dx (W^2) = 2 W^2 (d/dx W / W) \quad ((7))$$

The average momentum is a function of space which seems to imply acceleration, but unusual results arise. Consider:

$$d/dx (-i d/dx W / W) = m d/dx (v \text{ quantum average}) = -i d/dx d/dx W / W + i (d/dx W / W)^2 \quad ((8))$$

Thus, the quantum average momentum changes in space as the difference of quantum average kinetic energy and average momentum squared. The latter term is related to the change in physical density as it arises from the derivative of the denominator factor W. Thus, the quantum average of the kinetic energy is a main term driving the change in space (or acceleration) of the quantum average of momentum. Thus, this quantum average of momentum does not follow Newton's second law. For average momentum, one has the following conservation law:

$$d/dx \text{ Average quantum momentum} - i (\text{Average quantum momentum})^2 - i 2mV(x) = -2mi E \quad ((8))$$

Here $(\text{Average quantum momentum})^2$ cancels an equal term with opposite sign contained in the $d/dx p \text{ ave}$ term, leaving the quantum average of kinetic energy.

Thus, as argued in previous notes, it seems it is the quantum average kinetic energy which satisfies a classical energy conservation law. This seems to indicate there are two velocities in the quantum system, that associated with the quantum average potential and that associated with the quantum average kinetic energy. The later, which is consistent with Newton's second law, does not seem to have a simple physical interpretation as it is given by:

$$v_{KE}(x) = v(x) \text{ associated with quantum KE} = \text{sqrt} (-1/m^2 d/dx d/dx W / W) \quad ((8b))$$

It seems it would be good to derive this velocity from first principles associated with Newton's second law i.e.

$$v_{KE}(x) d/dx v_{KE}(x) = (1/m) F(x) \quad ((8c))$$

From the Schrodinger equation:

$$-1/2m (d/dx)^3 W / W + 1/2m (d/dx d/dx W / W)(d/dx W / W) = F(x) \quad ((8d))$$

It might be possible to assign a physical interpretation to ((8d)) as it is the difference between a kind of quantum average kinetic energy flux and the product of the overall quantum average KE and the quantum average momentum. From ((8d)) one is led to ((8c)), although this does not seem to have the interpretation of a flow that one might expect for a velocity which obeys Newton's law.

To see force enter into the picture, one needs to take the second derivative of ((8)). It is perhaps more interesting, however, to first take the second spatial derivative of the spatial density:

$$d/dx d/dx W^2 = 2 (d/dx W)^2 + 2 W d/dx d/dx W \quad ((9))$$

Thus, $d/dx W^2$ is related to the quantum average momentum, the second spatial derivative of density is related to the quantum average kinetic energy at x and the quantum average momentum squared, and the third derivative of W^2 to force:

$$(d/dx)^3 W^2 = -F 2mW^2 + 7 (d/dx W)(d/dx d/dx W) \quad ((10))$$

Thus, in quantum mechanics, spatial density is closely linked to the quantum average momentum, the quantum average kinetic energy and classical force. This is not the case in classical physics.

Conclusion

In conclusion, it seems that bound state quantum mechanics is based on 'quantum averaging' or interference as one uses an object called a wavefunction $W(x) = \text{Sum over } p \text{ } f_p \exp(ipx)$ to describe an ensemble of plane wave states in a potential. This has dramatic consequences on 'quantum averages' such as:

Quantum average momentum at $x = -id/dx W / W$ and

Quantum average kinetic energy = $-1/2m d/dx d/dx W / W$

as a classical approach might lead to the non-quantum results:

Quantum average momentum at $x = (\text{Sum over } p \text{ } p f_p) / (\text{Sum over } p \text{ } f_p)$ and a similar result for the quantum average kinetic energy.

The nonclassical quantum average momentum at x vanishes if f_p is even as p takes on positive and negative values. In quantum mechanics, however, there is an average momentum flux at each point x which is linked to d/dx spatial density. This flux changes from point to point, suggesting acceleration, but d/dx quantum average momentum is equal to the difference in quantum average kinetic energy and $1/2m$ quantum average momentum squared. Thus, its acceleration is like an energy. Quantum average kinetic energy, however, satisfies a classical energy conservation equation, thus there is a second velocity in the quantum system, that obtained from the quantum average kinetic energy which obeys Newton's second law. The spatial density W^2 in a quantum system changes to first order according to the quantum average momentum, to second order according to the quantum average kinetic energy and to third order according to a term proportional to classical force and a term proportional to the quantum average momentum multiplied by the quantum average kinetic energy.